

Quick Scoping Review - What are possible effective nutrition interventions for enhanced child health outcomes in Vietnam

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Here we outline a Quick Scoping Review with the review question: ‘What are possible effective nutrition interventions for enhanced child health outcomes in Vietnam’ We searched Google Scholar for papers, abstracts, thesis work, reports and other published documentation on the efficacy of food environment nutrition interventions for enhanced child health outcomes in Vietnam. We used the query "*Child nutrition*" + "*intervention*" + "*Vietnam*" + "*food environment*" and constrained the search to documents published since 2019. The search yielded **245** papers, **166** after removing duplicates and irrelevant work (e.g., bibliography only, journal homepage only).

The literature encompassed a range of topics, including public health, nutrition, and agricultural production and marketing. It included research findings, literature reviews, and conference proceedings on public health policy, community food security, the role of meat and fish in regional food systems, the social determinants of healthy eating, school food environments, and the relationship between farm diversity and diet diversity, among other relevant subjects.

The collection of publications also covered other topics regarding food environments and child nutrition more generally. The work addressed the impact of urbanization on food security, the role of Indigenous vegetables in sustainable food systems, and the importance of innovation in transforming food systems. It included studies on inequities and nutrition-related policies and guidelines in various countries. Public policy and planning can support local stakeholders in maintaining equitable and nutritious local food systems, particularly for positive child health outcomes. Many papers covered public health policy in developed countries. The literature emphasized the need to assess policy impacts and the lack of such approaches in development research. We pre-registered the search query on searchRxiv; the full bibliography can be found on the CABI digital library (Whitney et al., 2023).

Social and NGO Initiatives

Non-government and collective social action (Hurley, 2021) can support the care, maintenance, and social fabric of communities to create equitable nutrition (J. Chen, 2024; Mai et al., 2022) and positively affect child health outcomes (Athavale et al., 2020; I. D. Brouwer et al., 2021; Lane, 2023; Rahman et al., 2024). Groups can promote sustainability and equitable local food through advocacy, education, and initiatives such as school gardens.

Community food security through gardening

Community food security through gardening emerged in several papers. The research highlighted how community and home gardens can alleviate food insecurity (Buabeng & Aduteye, 2022) and enhance household well-being by increasing access to fresh produce (Di Prima, Wright, et al., 2022; Rousham et al., 2023). The literature underscores the positive impacts of community gardens (Bosch et al., 2021; Di Prima, Nguyen Dinh, et al., 2022; Di Prima, Wright, et al., 2022) and notes various government programs supporting these initiatives (Buabeng & Aduteye, 2022; Trübswasser et al., 2022). Community gardens can be grown on any community land, including school property (Di Prima, Wright, et al., 2022; Rousham et al., 2023).

Movement and physical activity

The literature provided examples of interventions for increasing physical activity for child health. These included cases such as the importance of ensuring safe travel for children to school while at the same time promoting physical activity to prevent weight gain (Iuliano et al., 2020). The trend towards driving children to school is unlikely to be reversed unless parents can be more confident that their children are safe on the streets (T. Nguyen et al., 2022; Powles, 2011). Sedentary activities are associated with weight gain in adolescents (Glen, 2019; Shekar & Popkin, 2020). Attractive and secure outdoor environments to encourage children to engage in physical activity and outdoor play are essential (Grasty, 2023).

Programs for nutrition assistance

Nutrition assistance programs such as the American SNAP (Supplemental Nutrition Assistance Program) can influence public health by affecting food security and diet quality. Social assistance programs, such as school meal provisions, aim to find alternatives for vulnerable children (Bleich, 2020; Borsellino et al., 2020) who rely on school meals (Egamberdiev, 2021; Finaret & Masters, 2019; Solihin et al., 2023). School meals, SNAP, and vouchers exist among other policy opportunities to strengthen public health, particularly child nutrition (Bertrand, 2019; Iuliano et al., 2020; Keats et al., 2020; Tekle et al., 2023).

School meals and nutrition education

School meals programs can promote healthy eating and improve nutrition outcomes. These programs offer nutrition education and behavior change tactics to improve health and prevent stunting (Rahman et al., 2024; Solihin et al., 2023). Including children, teachers, and parents in nutrition education can improve nutrition outcomes (Bertrand, 2019; I. D. Brouwer et al., 2021; Solihin et al., 2023; ten Hove & Guo, 2023).

Marketing and industry role in child health

The food industry's behavior and methods need modification to establish a more supportive food environment for child development. Social media (Keats et al., 2020; Ramakrishnan & Aimee, 2020; Solihin et al., 2023; Webb Girard et al., 2020), informative TV programs, radio soaps, and

vendor influence all play a role in promoting healthy food choices (Fadele et al., 2023; Kilimani et al., 2022; Lane, 2023). Consumer characteristics influence consumer motivations for adopting healthy foods along with other factors in the food environments, but market positioning also plays a strong role (Berti & Agostoni, 2022; Birhanu et al., 2021; R. Brouwer, 2021; Iuliano et al., 2020; Milsom, 2021; Storhaug et al., 2022; Tekle et al., 2023).

Animal-based food

Several papers covered the implications of meat consumption in regional food systems. This body of work explores the role of meat and fish in the nutrition of regional food systems, advocating for animal-based foods to enhance nutrition outcomes (Birhanu et al., 2021; D. Chen et al., 2021; Dumas et al., 2018; Elias et al., 2023; Häsler et al., 2018; JAYAWARDENA, 2020; Ramakrishnan & Aimee, 2020). It emphasizes the involvement of diverse actors in food systems to boost value (Birhanu et al., 2021; Cohen et al., 2021), reduce waste, and improve equity (Boakye & Akenteng, 2021) in meat production and consumption. Improving trade and implementing nutrition-sensitive governance around livestock and aquaculture can contribute to better nutrition outcomes (Bhandari, 2022; Cohen et al., 2021; Di Prima, Wright, et al., 2022).

Social determinants of healthy eating

Social determinants of healthy eating were a theme in many papers. The literature on developing and developed economies addressed challenges related to access to services, gender dynamics, and nutrition-sensitive agricultural practices (Bose et al., 2019; Cohen et al., 2021; Di Prima, Nguyen Dinh, et al., 2022; Owili, 2021; Powell et al., 2015; Uy et al., 2022). Material aspects, such as lack of access to safe and clean water and gendered dynamics, contribute to inequities in healthy eating (Bleich, 2020; Martin-Howard, 2019; Owili, 2021). The work suggests incorporating nutrition education into school curriculums and promoting school gardens to enhance healthy eating practices (Bertrand, 2019; D'Alessandro & Molina, 2021; Owili, 2021; Sills, 2023; Udari et al., 2021).

Health implications of school food environments

Several studies covered the health implications of school food environments. School food environments had a major impact on children's dietary behaviors throughout the literature (Bertrand, 2019; I. D. Brouwer et al., 2021; Fernandes et al., 2017; Iuliano et al., 2020; Lane, 2023; Mai et al., 2022; M. T. Nguyen, 2021; Nordhagen, 2020; Solihin et al., 2023; ten Hove & Guo, 2023; Udari et al., 2021). Many studies discussed the influence of free school meals (Bleich, 2020; Fernandes et al., 2017; Ming, 2020), the proximity of other shops (Carducci et al., 2018) and high-sugar foods close to schools, and the availability of foods for sale otherwise in and around schools on dietary diversity (Carducci et al., 2018; Iuliano et al., 2020; Trübswasser et al., 2022; Von Braun et al., 2023). Integration of nutrition information into the school curriculum (R. Brouwer, 2021; Glen, 2019; Ngan et al., 2018; T. Nguyen et al., 2021; Owili, 2021) and the involvement of government officials can improve nutrition knowledge and practices (ten Hove & Guo, 2023; Trübswasser et al., 2022).

Farm diversity and dietary diversity

Several of the papers covered the relationship between farm diversity and dietary diversity. Research findings indicate a positive relationship between farm production diversity and household dietary diversity in developed and developing country food environments (Amao et al., 2023; Birhanu et al., 2021; Jones et al., 2014; Mashingaidze et al., 2020; Moore et al., 2022; Nabuuma et al., 2022). Diverse farms can contribute to more varied diets for children (Birhanu et al., 2021; Di Prima, Wright, et al., 2022; Jones et al., 2014; Mashingaidze et al., 2020), with factors such as gender and household wealth affecting this relationship (Jones et al., 2014).

Urbanization and nutrition

Many of the documents covered the relationship between urbanization and its effect on nutrition. Rapid urbanization is associated with increased slum populations and exposure to poverty (Nsabimana et al., 2024; Umotho, 2023), limited access to services, and unsanitary conditions (Nsabimana et al., 2024). Poor child nutrition outcomes are prevalent in low- and middle-income countries due to urbanization and its associated challenges (Athavale et al., 2020; J. Chen, 2024; Ferraboschi et al., 2022; Graham, 2023; Jehn & Brewis, 2009; T. Nguyen et al., 2022). Urbanization is associated with household food insecurity, lack of food storage facilities, clean water, and electricity, all of which contribute to reduced diet diversity (Athavale et al., 2020; J. Chen, 2024; Ferraboschi et al., 2022; Graham, 2023; Jaacks & Di Cesare, 2022; T. Nguyen et al., 2022; Nsabimana et al., 2024).

Crop commercialization

A few studies covered the potential benefits of income through selling crops for farming households. The commercialization of crops can affect nutrient intake through increased crop income (Kilimani et al., 2022, 2022). Access to credit (Amao et al., 2023; Bhandari et al., 2022; Nordhagen et al., 2023; Storhaug et al., 2022; Trübswasser et al., 2022; Vuong, 2020), homestead gardens, and livestock rearing positively influence diet diversity and nutrition, particularly in developing countries (Bhandari, 2022; Bosch et al., 2021; Vuong, 2020).

Climate adaptation strategies and nutrition

Some studies assessed the impact of climate adaptation strategies on nutrition. Factors such as food environment, work/social environment, health environment, and living environment influence the impact of climate change on nutrition (Ferraboschi et al., 2022; Garde & Zrilic, 2020; Macheke et al., 2022; Manohar et al., 2023; Ridoutt & Turrini, 2024; Shekar & Popkin, 2020).

Gender and healthy food

Many studies reported on gender research to promote gender equality and empower women for an expected effect on child health. School feeding programs (I. D. Brouwer et al., 2021; CGIAR, 2021; Johnstone et al., 2023), credit access (Storhaug et al., 2022; Vuong, 2020), and women's empowerment contribute to increased diet diversity and improved nutrition outcomes (Adem,

2023; Birhanu et al., 2021; Johnstone et al., 2023; Makinwa & Kyobutungi, 2021). Women's decisions on food purchases and preparations are influenced by their children's food choices (I. D. Brouwer et al., 2021; Nordhagen, 2020) and the availability of resources (Vuong, 2020). Healthy foods can be incorporated into women's and children's diets (Bose et al., 2019; Chamoun, 2022; Mashingaidze et al., 2020). Education on the benefits of an intervention (i.e. palm weevil larvae for iron consumption in Ghanaian children (Chamoun, 2022)) and the involvement of children can promote its acceptance and consumption (Bertrand, 2019; M. T. Nguyen, 2021; Payan & Zahid, 2022; ten Hove & Guo, 2023). Food insecurity leads to various coping behaviors that have social and health ramifications, particularly for women and children (Chaudhuri et al., 2021). Policymakers should explore adaptive strategies to improve food availability, accessibility, utilization, and stability (Birhanu et al., 2021; Bleich, 2020; Finaret & Masters, 2019; Harris et al., 2022; Uddin et al., 2023).

Wild collected foods

Some papers discussed wild edible food and the importance for dietary diversity and nutrition. Consumption of wild plant foods is associated with inadequate nutrition among rural communities and children (Moore et al., 2022; Raneri et al., 2023). Wild foods play an important role in diets during lean seasons in many rural developing contexts (Manohar et al., 2023; Powell et al., 2013, 2015).

Benefit-risk analysis in food and nutrition

Several papers discussed the potential for risk assessment in development research for child nutrition. Risk assessments are often conducted to evaluate the safety and benefits of food and nutrition interventions (Athavale et al., 2020; Häsler et al., 2018), particularly for child health outcomes (Egamberdiev, 2021). Risk assessment can play a role in evaluating food safety (Tijhuis et al., 2012).

Household impact of the COVID-19 pandemic

Many studies discussed nutrition and the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic has had various household effects, including increased food insecurity for families and children. Childhood malnutrition increased, in the form of both over and undernutrition (Egamberdiev, 2021; Ferraboschi et al., 2022; Lane, 2023; Rahman et al., 2024; Rousham et al., 2023).

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